

Indonesian Local Wisdom as the Basis for People's Intentions to Buy Healthy Food

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: June 06, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: January 10, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Local Wisdom, Healthy food, Purchase Intention</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5834189</p>	<p><i>Indonesia is known to have a number of good habits related to consuming healthy food, but currently Indonesia is facing health problems, including obesity. This study aims to determine the factors that can contribute to encouraging people's intention to buy healthy food. The theory used refers to Krissoff's opinion, analyzed using the PLS-SEM tool, involving 368 respondents who live in the city of Jakarta and its surroundings. The results of the study show that Health, Environmentally Friendly and Product Quality factors, which are known to contribute to people's intention to buy healthy food products, can then be used to re-promote Indonesian local wisdom in terms of consuming healthy food.</i></p>

Introduction

As it is known, Indonesia as an archipelagic country, which has at least 17,000 islands, around 2,400 inhabited islands, and has around 1,340 ethnic groups (BPS, 2010) certainly has wealth in the form of diversity. It is imaginable that with so many ethnic groups, Indonesia certainly has a local culture that is also diverse in various aspects. As a country that can be called an agrarian country, of course, Indonesia also has a local culture that is closely related to agriculture, food and also suggestions for consuming healthy food. For example, in one of the tribes in Indonesia known as the Javanese tribe, there is a known eating etiquette, which is referred to as 'ojo dokoh'. This ethic recommends that a person does not consume food in excess (Parmanto, 2015). In addition, culinary heritage is also known in 2 (two) regions in Eastern Indonesia, namely the Maluku Islands and Papua. In both places, the staple food is called 'papeda' which is made from sago. It is known that this sago is gluten free and also rich in fiber, low in cholesterol and nutritious. Papeda has essential nutrients such as protein, carbohydrates, calcium, phosphorus, and iron (Lararenjana, 2020). Of course, there are many other local cultures in Indonesia that recommend producing and consuming healthy food. However, along the way, it was noted that Indonesia was experiencing obesity problems. The results of Riskesdas 2007-2018 show an increasing trend of 10.5% (2007), 14.8% (2013) and 21.8% (2018) in obesity cases in Indonesia (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2019). The prevalence of obesity in people aged 18 years and over also continues to increase. Starting from 8.6% in 2008, to 11.5% in 2013, and increasing to 13.6% in 2018 (CNN Indonesia, 2019). According to the latest Riskesdas data, there are 16 regions in Indonesia that have obesity rates higher than the national figure of 21.8%. The area with the highest obesity rate is North Sulawesi with an obesity rate of 30.2%, followed by DKI Jakarta, East Kalimantan, West Papua, Riau Islands, North Kalimantan and North Sumatra, North Maluku, Gorontalo, Aceh, Riau, Bangka Belitung, Bali, West Java, East Java and Banten (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2018).

In this era of globalization, almost all aspects of life have become more modern. This modernity is used as a reference to lead to improvements in every existing sector, such as technology, industry, infrastructure, lifestyle to human mindset and behavior (Hidayatullah, 2018). Especially in a big city like DKI Jakarta with a high level of mobility, people need things that are fast and instant. With these changing human needs, people have very limited time to really consider what to eat. As a result, many people prefer fast food which is high in calories, and is known as "junk food". The level of consumption of junk food in adolescents in Indonesia is currently relatively high, where the average teenager consumes 3 junk food up to 4 times a month (Arief et al., 2011). Fast food is synonymous with foods that are high in calories and low in micronutrients such as vitamins, minerals, amino acids, and fiber. High calorie and sugar content can contribute to obesity problems (Ashakiran & Deepthi, 2012). The low consumption of fruits and vegetables in Indonesia is thought to be the main cause of health problems ranging from obesity, cancer, stroke, chronic kidney disease, diabetes mellitus to hypertension. Referring to BPS data in 2016 the consumption of fruit and vegetables in Indonesian society reached 173 grams per day (Suara.com, 2018), this figure is smaller than the recommendations of the World Health Organization (WHO) which recommends consumption of fruits and vegetables for a healthy life of 400

grams per day (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2018). The government's recommendation through the Ministry of Health to consume up to 2-3 servings of fruit per day does not seem to be a priority for today's society. For this reason, the results of this study are expected to contribute to reminding the Indonesian people to have a healthy eating pattern as is well known in local culture in Indonesia. since a long time ago.

Problem Statement

The phenomenon of changes in diet in Indonesia is currently faced with various health problems, one of which is obesity. The prevalence of obesity in Indonesia continued to increase from 10.5% in 2008, to 14.8% in 2013, and jumped to 21.8% in 2018. Responding to the increasing obesity epidemic in Indonesia, the Government created the Nusantara Movement to Reduce Obesity Rates (GENTAS) to push the obesity rate to 15.4%. One of the goals is to increase public awareness to consume healthy foods (Directorate General of Disease Prevention and Control, 2017). Obesity is also caused by the current lack of public awareness of healthy food consumption. The emergence of a healthy food trend in Indonesia in early 2016 provided new hope to help reduce obesity rates. This also affects changes in people's consumption patterns to become people who care about their health. However, several researchers explain that consumer interest in healthy food is not, at least not yet, followed by people's intentions to make healthy food a primary need. In fact, local culture in many places in Indonesia, is very familiar with healthy food and also strongly recommends consuming healthy food. This research focuses on the notion of consuming healthy food in the form of an intention to buy healthy food.

Research Questions

Based on the description above, the research questions can be described as follows:

1. Does health affect consumers' purchase intention towards healthy food?
2. Does food safety affect consumers' purchase intentions for healthy food?
3. Does environmental friendliness affect consumers' purchase intentions for healthy food?
4. Does product quality affect consumers' purchase intention on healthy food?

Research Objectives:

In line with the research questions above, the objectives of this study are to:

1. Knowing the effect of health on the intention to buy healthy food products.
2. Knowing the effect of food safety on the intention to buy healthy food products.
3. Knowing the effect of environmentally friendly on the intention to buy healthy food products.
4. Knowing the effect of product quality on the purchase intention of healthy food products.

Literature Review

There are many theories related to healthy food and its relation to the decision to buy healthy food. One of the theories that is often used as the basis for research is the one put forward by Krissoff in 1988. Although this theory is related to organic food, it is used in this study, and it means that organic food has the same characteristics as healthy food. This is also in line with the opinion of Molyneaux in 2007, in a paper submitted by Wee et.al. in 2014. In the research model conducted by Wee et.al it is stated that Intention to purchase, in this case of course buying healthy food, will be related to Health, Food Safety, Environmental Friendly and Product Quality.

Health

Of course, in general, everyone will give priority to their health. However, sometimes visible behavior is not always in line with this spirit. An understanding of the concept of health is considered very important to help provide awareness to the public about the importance of overall health. Awareness of health is realized as the starting point for efforts to maintain health, and increase motivation to maintain, maintain health and quality of life by implementing a healthy lifestyle (Michaelidou & Hassan, 2008). Thus, the intention to buy healthy food is also important.

Food Safety

What is meant by food safety in this case is food that is safe for consumption, of course for the long term. For this reason, matters relating to food safety will be one of the factors driving people to seek, buy and consume safer food (Lockie, et al., 2004). Smith (2008) defines food safety as a condition and effort to ensure food quality, free from contamination and foodborne diseases, so that it is safe for consumption.

Environmentally Friendly

It is known that more and more people are increasingly concerned about the environment, and of course this has a positive impact on the selection of healthy food products and does not have a negative impact on the environment. This can also be seen from the increasing public demand for agricultural products produced by processes that have little impact on the environment (Chinnici, 2002). Therefore, concern for the environment will remain one of the reasons for people's intentions when purchasing food.

Product Quality

Many experts have expressed their opinions regarding product quality, including Kotler and Armstrong (2010) who state that product and service quality, customer satisfaction and company profitability are three closely related matters. The relationship that occurs is, the higher the level of quality, the higher the level of satisfaction generated. For this reason, it is easy to understand that product quality is very important to deliver customer satisfaction.

Purchase Intention

Purchase Intention can be defined as the intention of a person to take an action, such as to decide to buy a product or service (Mowen & Minor, 2006). Another opinion was expressed by Kotler (2005) which states that Purchase Intention is something that occurs before every public decision to buy something, in this case of course including buying healthy food. Based on the above definition, Purchase Intention can be interpreted as one of the processes in buying a product or service, before someone finally decides to buy the product. Purchase Intention appears driven by someone's desire to buy a product based on their needs. In short, Purchase Intention is a person's mental condition that reflects a purchase plan for a particular product.

Thus, the theoretical framework in this research will be in the form as can be seen in the section below.

Figure 1 Theoretical Framework
Source: Adapted from Krissoff in Wee et., al. (2014)

Research hypothesis

Based on the description above, the research hypothesis applied in this study is as can be seen in the following section.

- H1: Health has a positive effect on purchase intention of healthy food products.
- H2: Food safety has a positive effect on purchase intentions of healthy food products.
- H3: Environmentally friendly has a positive effect on the purchase intention of healthy food products.
- H4: Product quality has a positive effect on purchase intentions of healthy food products.

Method

The method used to analyze the data in this study refers to a reference based on a simultaneous analysis process associated with a multivariable research model, namely Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). Partial Least Square (SEM) structural equation model was used in this study to confirm causality and the relationship between all the factors stated in this study.

This study involved 368 respondents, who live around the city of Jakarta, the capital city of Indonesia, and the age range is 18-40 years. The questionnaire was prepared based on the theoretical framework as mentioned in the previous section. From the theoretical framework above, it is known that there are 5 (five) variables, and from each of these variables an indicator is sought. The source of the search for these indicators of course comes from several related scientific journals. From these indicators, the statements in the research questionnaire were compiled, and answers were provided on the basis of a Likert scale. The distribution of questionnaires was carried out from October 2019 to January 2020, both online and offline. The selection of respondents was based on a non-probability sampling technique, namely purposive sampling.

As is usual in a study using a self-administered questionnaire as a data acquisition tool, it is necessary to do a pre-test. The validity test is carried out through the calculation of the Pearson Product Moment correlation, while the reliability test is carried out through calculations using the Cronbach Alpha calculation tool. In more detail, the stages of the research carried out can be seen in the section below.

Figure 2 Research Framework
Source: Developed by Researcher

Note:

PPM = Pearson Product Moment

CA = Cronbach Alpha

SEM = Structural Equation Modelling

Results and Discussion

As described above, the first step taken at this stage is to conduct a pre-test, as follows.

Validity Test

In this study, 15 samples were used for pre-test with a significance level of 0.05. A statement can be said to be valid if the results of the Pearson Product Moment correlation are more than 0.514. Statements with Pearson Correlation results below 0.514 are declared invalid and will be eliminated. The results of this test for each variable can be seen as follows.

a. Health

Table 1 Validity of Health

Items	R- table	R compute value	Result
H1	0.514	0.835	Valid
H2	0.514	0.618	Valid
H3	0.514	0.628	Valid
H4	0.514	0.792	Valid
H5	0.514	0.507	Invalid
H6	0.514	0.765	Valid
H7	0.514	0.610	Valid
H8	0.514	0.722	Valid
H9	0.514	0.789	Valid
H10	0.514	0.401	Invalid
H11	0.514	0.615	Valid
H12	0.514	0.718	Valid
H13	0.514	0.707	Valid
H14	0.514	0.677	Valid

Source: Data processed by Researcher

b. Food Safety

Table 2 Validity of Food Safety

Items	R- table	R compute value	Result
FS1	0.514	0.755	Valid
FS2	0.514	0.669	Valid
FS3	0.514	0.902	Valid
FS4	0.514	0.728	Valid
FS5	0.514	0.773	Valid

Source: Data processed by Researcher

c. Environmentally Friendly

Table 3 Validity of Environmentally Friendly

Items	R- table	R compute value	Result
EF1	0.514	0.519	Valid
EF2	0.514	0.813	Valid
EF3	0.514	0.785	Valid
EF4	0.514	0.807	Valid

Items	R- table	R compute value	Result
EF5	0.514	0.438	Invalid
EF6	0.514	0.609	Valid

Source: Data processed by Researcher

d. Product Quality

Table 4 Validity of Product Quality

Items	R- table	R compute value	Result
PQ1	0.514	0.823	Valid
PQ2	0.514	0.804	Valid
PQ3	0.514	0.798	Valid
PQ4	0.514	0.650	Valid
PQ5	0.514	0.611	Valid
PQ6	0.514	0.662	Valid
PQ7	0.514	0.555	Valid
PQ8	0.514	0.608	Valid
PQ9	0.514	0.533	Valid
PQ10	0.514	0.732	Valid
PQ11	0.514	0.710	Valid
PQ 12	0.514	0.672	Valid

Source: Data processed by Researcher

e. Purchase Intention

Table 5 Validity of Purchase Intention

Items	R- table	R compute value	Result
PI1	0.514	0.632	Valid
PI2	0.514	0.736	Valid
PI3	0.514	0.563	Valid
PI4	0.514	0.722	Valid
PI5	0.514	0.551	Valid
PI6	0.514	0.593	Valid
PI7	0.514	0.819	Valid
PI8	0.514	0.849	Valid
P9	0.514	0.819	Valid
PI10	0.514	0.697	Valid
PI11	0.514	0.861	Valid

Source: Data processed by Researcher

Reliability Test

The results of the Reliability Test, using the Cronbach Alpha tool, gave the following results.

Table 6 Reliability Test

Variables	Cronbach Alpha	Description
Health Understanding (X1)	0.923	Good
Food Safety (X2)	0.904	Good
Environmentally Friendly (X3)	0.873	Good
Product Quality (X4)	0.954	Good
Purchase Intention (Y)	0.937	Good

Source: Data processed by Researcher

As stated in the previous section, based on the calculations above, the questionnaires that were redistributed were those that did not include invalid statements.

SEM Model

From the results of distributing questionnaires, then an analysis was carried out using the Smart PLS-SEM analysis tool, and resulted in the following model.

Figure 3 SEM Model
Source: Analysis result

Outer Model Measurement

Basically, the measurement of this outer model will involve Convergent validity, Composite reliability, and Discriminant validity, as follows.

Convergent Validity

Construct validity testing can be done by observing whether or not there is a strong correlation between the construct and construct indicators, resulting in the following calculation.

Table 7 Convergent Validity

Variable	Indicator	Loading Factor	Information
Health	H 1	0.801	Valid
	H 3	0.643	Valid
	H 4	0.687	Valid
	H 5	0.671	Valid
	H 6	0.676	Valid
	H 7	0.748	Valid
	H 10	0.736	Valid

Variable	Indicator	Loading Factor	Information
Food Safety	FS 1	0.730	Valid
	FS 2	0.824	Valid
	FS 3	0.811	Valid
	FS 4	0.782	Valid
	FS 5	0.796	Valid
Environmental Friendly	EF 1	0.764	Valid
	EF2	0.863	Valid
	EF 3	0.859	Valid
	EF 4	0.854	Valid
	EF 5	0.767	Valid
Product Quality	PQ 1	0.690	Valid
	PQ 2	0.723	Valid
	PQ 3	0.651	Valid
	PQ 5	0.601	Valid
	PQ 7	0.694	Valid
	PQ 8	0.775	Valid
	PQ 10	0.634	Valid
	PQ 11	0.663	Valid
	PQ 12	0.752	Valid
Purchase Intention	PI 1	0.721	Valid
	PI 2	0.758	Valid
	PI 3	0.791	Valid
	PI 4	0.819	Valid
	PI 5	0.801	Valid
	PI 6	0.812	Valid
	PI 7	0.809	Valid
	PI 8	0.807	Valid
	PI 9	0.800	Valid
	PI 10	0.801	Valid
	PI 11	0.850	Valid

Source: Analysis result

Convergent validity can be seen from the loading factor for each construct indicator. The rule of thumb used to assess convergent validity is that the loading factor value must be greater than 0.6. Table 7 above shows indicators with a loading factor value greater than 0.6 and is said to be valid. There are 5 indicators on the Health variable with a loading factor value less than 0.6 and said to be invalid, there are also 3 indicators on the Product Quality variable with a loading factor value less than 0.6 and said to be invalid.

Composite Reliability

The reliability of the research instrument in this study was tested using composite reliability, average variance extracts (AVE), and the Cronbach Alpha coefficient. A construct is said to be reliable if the composite reliability and Cronbach alpha values are above 0.7 and the AVE value is above 0.4. Some references state that reliability is still acceptable if the Composite Reliability value is above 0.6. The following are the results of data analysis from composite reliability and Cronbach alpha.

Table 8 Cronbach Alpha

Variable	Cronbach Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Health	0.837	0.877	0.530
Food Safety	0.848	0.892	0.623
Environmental Friendly	0.880	0.913	0.677
Product Quality	0.861	0.890	0.475
Purchase Intention	0.943	0.951	0.637

Source: Analysis result

The test results based on table 8 above show that the results of Composite Reliability and Cronbach alpha show a satisfactory value, namely the Cronbach Alpha value and the reliability value of each variable, namely Health,

Food Safety, Environmental Friendly, Product Quality, Purchase Intention more than 0.6 . The AVE results also show a satisfactory value, where all AVE values for all variables are also above 0.4. This shows the consistency and stability of the instrument used is high. In other words, all the constructs or variables of this study have become suitable measuring instruments, and all statements used to measure each construct have high reliability.

Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity can be measured by looking at the value of the Cross loading factor by comparing the loading value of the intended construct to be greater than the loading value of the other constructs. The output of Smart-PLS will be explained in table 9 as follows

Table 9 Discriminant Validity

	EF	FS	H	PI	PQ
EF1	0.764	0.699	0.602	0.493	0.543
EF2	0.863	0.664	0.533	0.536	0.561
EF3	0.859	0.499	0.52	0.509	0.551
EF4	0.854	0.573	0.565	0.579	0.534
EF5	0.767	0.439	0.519	0.515	0.572
FS1	0.465	0.73	0.419	0.493	0.503
FS2	0.527	0.824	0.444	0.411	0.395
FS3	0.592	0.811	0.49	0.462	0.53
FS4	0.571	0.782	0.481	0.428	0.424
FS5	0.6	0.796	0.497	0.427	0.457
H1	0.514	0.454	0.801	0.582	0.498
H10	0.537	0.479	0.736	0.637	0.553
H3	0.389	0.244	0.643	0.428	0.373
H4	0.441	0.445	0.687	0.481	0.408
H5	0.423	0.351	0.671	0.413	0.476
H6	0.396	0.389	0.676	0.539	0.535
H7	0.568	0.519	0.748	0.626	0.509
PI1	0.479	0.57	0.532	0.721	0.515
PI10	0.464	0.378	0.608	0.801	0.49
PI11	0.475	0.403	0.606	0.85	0.497
PI2	0.478	0.403	0.577	0.758	0.5
PI3	0.521	0.463	0.557	0.79	0.599
PI4	0.571	0.479	0.618	0.818	0.572
PI5	0.597	0.571	0.668	0.8	0.541
PI6	0.511	0.416	0.64	0.813	0.614
PI7	0.478	0.47	0.623	0.81	0.613
PI8	0.523	0.351	0.638	0.808	0.554
PI9	0.517	0.467	0.576	0.801	0.538
PQ1	0.502	0.438	0.431	0.474	0.69
PQ10	0.356	0.259	0.414	0.377	0.634
PQ11	0.431	0.391	0.404	0.38	0.663
PQ12	0.484	0.472	0.49	0.494	0.752
PQ2	0.443	0.395	0.449	0.521	0.723
PQ3	0.45	0.31	0.404	0.474	0.651
PQ5	0.486	0.497	0.554	0.535	0.601
PQ7	0.416	0.385	0.389	0.4	0.694
PQ8	0.543	0.46	0.616	0.546	0.775

Source: Analysis result

From table 9, the discriminant validity test above shows that the cross loading value of each item on its construct (shaded box) is greater than the loading value with other constructs. From these results it can be concluded that there is no problem in discriminant validity. All indicators have a higher correlation coefficient in each construct than the indicator correlation coefficient value in the construct block in other columns. Likewise with other indicator correlations, it is concluded that each indicator in the block is a constructor in the column, which means it has a good discriminant validity value.

Inner Model Measurement

After evaluating the model and knowing that each construct has met the requirements of Convergent Validity, Discriminant Validity, and Composite Reliability, the next step is the evaluation of the structural model which includes testing of path coefficients, and R-Square.

Table 10 R-Square Coefficients

Variable	R-Square	R-Square Adjusted
Purchase Intention	0.642	0.638

Source: Analysis result

Based on table 10, the R-Square for Purchase Intention value is 0.642, which means that 64% of the variation or change in Purchase Intention is influenced by the variables of Health, Food Safety, Environmental Friendly, and Product Quality. The results after adjusting the model obtained an R-Square Adjusted Purchase Intention value of 0.638, which means that 63.8% of variations or changes in Purchase Intentions are influenced by Health, Food Safety, Environmental Friendly, and Product Quality variables while the remaining 46.2% is explained by other reasons. . Based on this, the results of the calculation of the Purchase Intention of the R-Square indicate that the R-Square is classified as moderate.

Bootstrapping

In PLS, each relationship is tested using a simulation using the sample bootstrap method. This test aims to minimize the problem of abnormalities in research. The test results using the bootstrap method from PLS are as follows:

Figure 4 Path Coefficient Measurement
Source: Analysis result

Hypothesis Testing

To see the significance of the effect of Health on Purchase Intention, the effect of Food Safety on Purchase Intention, the effect of Environmentally Friendly on Purchase Intention, by looking at the parameter coefficient values and the statistical significance value of t. The output of Smart-PLS using count-PLS Bootstrapping is as follows:

Table 11 Structural Model Test Result

Hypotheses	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Information
Health -> Purchase Intention	9.061	0.000	Accepted
Food Safety -> Purchase Intention	1.183	0.238	Rejected
Environmental Friendly -> Purchase Intention	2.162	0.031	Accepted
Product Quality -> Purchase Intention	4.991	0.000	Accepted

Source: Analysis result

As a consideration for hypothesis decision making is accepted if the value of t value \geq t table (1.96). Based on table 11, it can be known and concluded:

1. Health affects Purchase Intention. This can be seen from the path coefficient output obtained by t count $>$ t table ($9.061 > 1.96$), so that the hypothesis is accepted.
2. Food Safety has no effect on Purchase Intention. This can be seen from the path coefficient output obtained by the value of t count $<$ t table ($1.183 < 1.96$), so that the hypothesis is rejected.
3. Environmental Friendly affects Purchase Intention. This can be seen from the path coefficient output obtained by t count $>$ t table ($2.162 > 1.96$), so that the hypothesis is accepted.
4. Product Quality affects Purchase Intention. This can be seen from the path coefficient output obtained by t count $>$ t table ($4.991 > 1.96$), so that the hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion

This study illustrates the relationship between health understanding variables, food safety understandings, environmentally friendly understandings, product quality understandings, and buying interest. Based on the results of research and discussion in the previous chapter, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. From the results of this test, it shows that consumer understandings of health have a positive and significant effect on purchase intention. This shows that the higher a person's awareness of health, the higher his understanding of healthy food. Understandings about healthy food can be increased by increasing one's awareness of health so that the interest in buying healthy food products is higher.
2. Consumer understanding of food safety has no significant effect on Purchase Intention. This means that when the consumer's understanding of food safety changes, it will not cause a significant change to the purchase intention of healthy food.
3. Consumer Understanding of Environmentally Friendly has a significant positive effect on Purchase Intention. This means that when the consumer's understanding of environmentally friendly changes, it will cause a significant change in the intention to buy healthy food.
4. Consumer Understanding of Product Quality has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Interest. This shows that the higher a person's awareness of the quality of the food he consumes, the higher his understanding of healthy food so that the higher his interest in buying healthy food.

Thus, in an effort to encourage people to continue to consume or to buy healthy food, efforts can be made to remind and promote some good habits from local wisdom that have existed for a long time in Indonesia. For example, in terms of encouraging an understanding of the importance of health stemming from the habit of consuming healthy food, the effort that can be done is to re-promote various kinds of Indonesian specialties made from vegetables and/or fruit. Some examples of Indonesian food made from fruit are 'pacri nanas' (originating from the city of Pontianak, West Kalimantan province), which is made from pineapple, 'tempoyak' (originating from Palembang, Jambi and Bengkulu, in the southern part of the island of Sumatra), made from durian fruit, 'sayur sirsak' (from the province of West Java) which is made from soursop fruit. Indonesia also has a variety of foods such as salads. This food is usually made from kale, long beans, bean sprouts, spinach, tofu, tempeh and doused with peanut sauce. Examples of these foods include pecel (from Yogyakarta, Central Java and East Java, it is said that the meaning of the word 'pecel' is something that has been squeezed), gado-gado (from Jakarta and East Java, and the meaning of the word 'gado-gado' is a mixture), urap (from Central Java, and the meaning of the word 'urap' is harmony). Taking into account the description above, it can be seen that food also has a deep meaning in local wisdom in Indonesia. This example of meaning is also in line with the motto of the Indonesian state, namely Bhineka Tunggal Ika, which means 'different but still one'. A potential tradition that deserves to be re-promoted, in the midst of the pressure of technological advancement and globalization.

Recommendations

Based on the results and discussion above that have been explained, several things that can be used as recommendations are:

1. Business owner and/or manufacturers of healthy food should be more determined in promotional activities. Promotions that further highlight health aspects will have more influence to increase consumers' understanding of healthy food. So it will affect consumer purchase intentions.
2. Healthy food manufacturers are advised to provide food safety labels on their products, to provide complete information to consumers. This will increase understanding about healthy food and in turn will increase purchase intention.

3. Healthy food producers need to market healthy food products by maintaining product quality. Certification needs to be done to ensure product quality.

It is also recommended that the efforts mentioned above utilize local wisdom that has been known, but has been sidelined by technological developments and modernization. It is time for local wisdom to return to being the basis for behavior, in this case the behavior of consuming healthy food.

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